

PERMEABILITY EVALUATION IN VACUUM-ASSISTED RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS

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BACKGROUND

● Vacuum-assisted Resin Transfer Molding; VaRTM

Low Cost, Freedom in Design ○
Mechanical Properties △(Occurrence of Void and Dry Spot)

Optimize of Molding Condition by Flow Simulation

● Permeability

Defined in Darcy's Law, Flowability of Matrix Resin
Input Parameter for Flow Simulation

Problem Experimental Scatter **Large**, BENCHMARK ×

Purpose Examination of Permeability Measurements for Reducing Error

Factors of Scatter

① Race-tracking; Fluid's Flow between Preform and Mold

② Nesting; Phase Shift of Fabric Weave Difference in **Gap between Fiber Yarns**, **Thickness**

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEEDING

● Calculation of Permeability derived from Darcy's Law

$$K_{ex} \cdot t = \frac{\mu \cdot \phi \cdot x_{ff}^2}{2P_{vac}} = F \begin{cases} K_{ex}: \text{Permeability} [m^2] \\ t, \text{ time [s]}, \mu; \text{ Resin Viscosity [mPa}\cdot\text{s]} \\ \phi; \text{ Porosity [-]}, P_{vac}; \text{ Vacuum Pressure [Pa]} \\ x_{ff}; \text{ Position of Flow Front [m]} \end{cases}$$

● Material

Plain Woven Carbon Fiber Fabric

CK6261C, Toray, Number of Fibers: 12K
400 mm × 100 mm, 0° direction, 4 plies

2 Pack Type Epoxy Resin

XNR6815/XNH6815, Nagase Chemtex
Mixing Weight Ratio 100:30

● Fabric Preparation

1. Using Glue for Restriction of Fabric Deformation
2. Pulling out 0° Fiber Yarns at Both Ends
3. Weave Shift as Nesting

● Measurement for Position of Flow Front

$$x_{ff} = 400 \times \frac{N_i}{N_i + N_u} \text{ [mm]}$$

N_i : Pixels for Impregnated Area
 N_u : Pixels for Unimpregnated Area

Quantitative Evaluation for Effect of Race-tracking to Permeability

● VaRTM Equipment (Simultaneous)

Cancel the Difference of Epoxy Resin Condition

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

● Shape of Flow Front

Nearly Parallel to Weft Fiber Yarn

- Range of Race-tracking; Restricted
- Effect of Race-tracking to Permeability **REDUCE**

● Measured Permeability

In Simultaneous Measurement; **Not coincide**

→ Difference in Microstructure of Preforms
Experimental Scatter [2 plies] < [4, 8 plies]

2 plies;

Difference between K_{Bottom} and K_{Area} < 10%
Reproducibility; **Enough**

Mainly Distributed in $0.6-0.7 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$

Fabric Preparation and Materials Arrangement
for Controlling Race-tracking and Nesting Conditions

Effective

Permeability for Plain Woven Carbon Fiber Fabric / Epoxy Resin; $0.6-0.7 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$